

POWER TO THE PEOPLE OF EMDRUPVEJ

*How one street can inspire community building and
ecological restoration with the doughnut economy
framework*

COMMUNITY

“HOW ONE STREET CAN
INSPIRE COMMUNITY BUILDING
AND ECOLOGICAL RESTORATION
WITH THE DOUGHNUT ECONOMY
FRAMEWORK”

STRATEGIC PLANNING FOR URBAN NATURE 2024 - 2025

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01 INTRODUCTION

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1.1. Purpose and Background

The planet is on track for a +3°C temperature rise by the end of this century, surpassing critical tipping points and threatening food supplies, energy security, biodiversity, and the stability of much of the global economy (Wong et al., 2024). At the local level, cities are grappling with challenges such as urban sprawl, high population density, limited green spaces, poor air quality, and vulnerability to the severe impacts of anthropogenic climate change (Haaland & Konijnendijk, 2015). These urban issues are often intertwined with social problems, including isolation, loneliness, weak community connections, and a general lack of well-being, particularly in underserved neighborhoods (Moore et al., 2023).

Copenhagen is widely recognized as a global leader in green and sustainable development. However, despite its reputation, the Copenhagen Municipality is currently exceeding several planetary boundary parameters and remains insufficiently prepared to endure extreme weather events (Copenhagen Municipality, 2024). In June 2020, the City Council (Borgerrepræsentationen) reinforced its commitment to sustainability by decisively voting (50 - 4) to adopt Doughnut Economy as a guiding framework for the city's economic model (Steen Nielsen, 2020; Copenhagen Municipal Agency for Finance, 2021). Since 2023, the municipality has produced annual "Doughnut Reports" to assess Copenhagen's progress

toward achieving social and ecological balance (Copenhagen Municipality, 2024). These reports underscore critical areas that demand urgent action to transform Copenhagen into a socially inclusive and environmentally resilient city.

While these assessments have provided valuable insights, the city has yet to work consis-

"A neighbour-led transition could enable the deep retrofit of our homes, streets, public squares, high streets and schools, the transformation of our empty spaces into regenerative physical infrastructure to meet the needs of our communities, the rebuilding of our responsibility to more than human neighbours, and the rewilding of our homes and hearts." (Johar et al. 2024)

tently and strategically on implementing Doughnut-compatible initiatives, (Søgaard, 2022). Moreover, citizens have not been sufficiently involved in shaping Copenhagen's transition toward a sustainable future (Valeur, 2021).

Recognizing this gap, Copenhagen Municipality has invited Socio-Ecological Landscapes Consultancy (SELC) to help take the first step in a bold new direction: transforming Emdrupvej into a living laboratory for experimentation and co-creation. The Copenhagen Municipality has dedicated an unlimited budget to realize this strategy, which is being implemented as an initial four-year pilot project in Emdrup. Following this period and depending on the outcomes, the initiative may either be extended to build on existing efforts or expanded upon to another area in Copenhagen.

This also comes from the realization that now more than ever, we must invest in urban communities to retrofit spaces that meet human needs within the planet's ecological limits (Agger & Tortzen, 2023; Buijs et al., 2019). This is especially true for streets like Emdrupvej, situated in one of Copenhagen's most deprived areas (Copenhagen Municipality, 2021). Like most urban areas in Denmark, Emdrupvej faces the urgent task of addressing complex, interconnected multi-scale ecological and social challenges. This requires a collective reimagining of how communities and economies function.

Emdrupvej has been chosen as the canvas and laboratory for this initiative due to its long-standing challenges stemming from poor urban planning. The area faces significant issues, including air and noise pollution and a lack of social cohesion, making it a prime candidate for experiments with citizen-led refurbishment and joint implementation of innovative green solutions.

The aim of this report is to provide a strategic plan for addressing local social and ecological challenges at Emdrupvej while upholding the broader commitment to global sustainability, as outlined in the Doughnut Framework (explained in depth in section 3 of this report). Through this initiative, Emdrupvej will serve as a canvas for inclusive approaches that bring together diverse stakeholders—citizens, businesses, and institutions—to collaboratively envision and implement solutions for a thriving community with social continuity and ecological health.

This report outlines the principles, strategies, and actions that can guide Emdrupvej toward becoming a socially inclusive and ecologically balanced neighborhood. By doing so, it seeks to demonstrate how local action, rooted in community participation and aligned with global sustainability goals, can pave the way for transformative change in a neighborhood which hopefully can inspire many other local areas and municipalities.

We invite the Copenhagen Municipality, citi-

zens, and local stakeholders to view this plan not as a final blueprint but as a starting point for collective action and ongoing learning. Together, we can reimagine what it means to create a city where people and nature flourish in balance.

1.2. The Vision

We envision Emdrupvej as a model for urban development rooted in community engagement and environmental sustainability. Central to this vision is the revitalization of social and organizational networks through the empowerment of local democracy. By fostering open communication and collaborative decision-making among diverse stakeholders, we aim to create a resilient community. This transformation will be driven by opportunities for co-creation, capacity-building, and the collective implementation of sustainable solutions, ensuring that Emdrupvej thrives as a dynamic and connected urban ecosystem.

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TO BECOME A THRIVING AND
INCLUSIVE SPACE FOR ALL,
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PARTICIPATION, CONNECTION,
AND ACCESS TO NATURE, WHILE
RESPECTING THE WELLBEING OF
ALL PEOPLE AND THE HEALTH
OF THE PLANET.”

1.3. Strategy Summary

This report begins with a brief history of Ryparken-Lundehus - the neighbourhood where Emdrupvej is located. We identify existing governance and development structures, along with the main social, environmental and economic challenges in the area. Being that environmental justice is centered in our vision, it is also important to contextualize the site within the global environmental crisis and the international and national climate targets that have been set in larger forums. Climate mitigation and adaptation, along with the social and ecological needs of the neighborhood inform our methods, measurements and suggested designs within the strategy.

We go on to introduce Kate Raworth's Doughnut Economy Framework (DEAL, 2024a) to address the tensions of social and ecological challenges between the local and global scales. An explanation of this framework and its linked methodology is given along with examples of its application in Amsterdam, Netherlands and Grønlikaia, Norway. Finally SELC applies the Doughnut Framework to the case of Emdrupvej. This section also provides an overview of how SELC plans to community organise and identifies key stakeholders.

The participatory and physical initiatives that are laid out in this strategy have been curated by SELC using qualitative and quantitative data from the area, and the expertise of consultancy members. However, the initiatives are merely suggestions; it is SELC's hope that

these initiatives inspire the community to organize, take power, and create initiatives that suit the unique needs of the locality. By using Emdrupvej and creating spaces and events for community participation, local residents and stakeholders can be involved in identifying and tackling challenges while sharing knowledge, ideas and building comradery. This participatory approach ensures that the project reflects the specific needs and aspirations of the community.

The strategy concludes with the implementation framework-how this plan can be set into action. Beginning with a kick-off event for the community to introduce the principles of the Doughnut Framework and the global network of cities who participate, the neighborhood will venture into a cycle of imagination, creation, implementation and iteration- a cycle where initiatives will be born and the area will begin to evolve into a more socially resilient and ecologically-sensitive place. Recommendations for measuring and monitoring the project are laid out as well.

02 CONTEXT

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2.1. Emdrupvej in Ryparken-Lundehus

Ryparken-Lundehus is a primarily residential neighborhood, located on the boundary between the Bispebjerg and Østerbro districts of Copenhagen and characterized by a mix of social housing apartments and single-family homes. The neighborhood is also home to educational institutions, such as the Emdrup campus of Aarhus University, located just North of Emdrup Station. The area includes 5 main public greenspaces in the neighborhood, including Emdrup Lake, an artificial reservoir created around 1550 to enhance Copenhagen's water supply.

Ryparken-Lundehus has undergone significant transformations over the decades, evolving from an agricultural area to a mixed-use residential district, with a fast suburban and urban development in the 1940's (Linvald, 1975). Although some green areas were maintained through "The green consideration" in 1930, this densification has left its mark on the urban structure of Ryparken-Lundehus and, in some cases, the soil quality, which lead to a neighborhood that lacks alignment with the current sustainability and biodiversity principles for the city.

Figure 1: Emdrupvej in Ryparken-Lundehus

2.2. Emdrupvej as the Canvas

Emdrupvej has been selected as the focus of the pilot project because it represents a microcosm of the environmental and social challenges faced by the broader neighborhood. To effectively address the challenges and opportunities of Emdrupvej, a thorough analysis was conducted to better understand its environmental and social dynamics.

2.2.1 Methodology

The diagnosis of Emdrupvej was primarily based on surveys conducted by ARUP, providing detailed insights specific to the street (ARUP, 2023). Additionally, data from a broader survey by the Municipality of Copenhagen (2021) offered valuable context on the wider Ryparken-Lundehus district, helping to frame the neighborhood's challenges and opportunities.

2.2.2 Environmental Diagnosis

Air Pollution

The area faces significant environmental challenges that stem from urban densification and ongoing urbanization. Located between two major roads, between Lyngbyvej and Tuborgvej, Emdrupvej experiences notable air quality issues, largely driven by high traffic volumes and limited vegetation which would otherwise act as natural filters. The nearby highway, Helsingørmotorvejen, also contributed notably to this issue (Fig. 2). This perception of excessive traffic and pollution is reflected more broadly across Ryparken-Lundehus, as highlighted by a municipal survey in which 80% of respondents agreed on this issue (Municipality of Copenhagen, 2021). The absence

of green infrastructure, such as tree canopies and green corridors, exacerbates the problem, leaving residents exposed to elevated levels of pollutants. This not only impacts health but also diminishes the overall environmental quality of the neighborhood.

Noise Pollution

Noise pollution is another environmental stressor affecting Emdrupvej due to high traffic volumes, particularly in areas close to Lyngbyvej and Tuborgvej roads and the highway. Without sufficient green buffers or sound-absorbing vegetation, noise levels remain persistently high, disrupting residents' well-being and reducing the attractiveness of public spaces.

Landscape Fragmentation

The district has been significantly impacted by urban densification, leading to landscape fragmentation, isolating habitats, and reducing the movement of flora and fauna. The disruption of these connections poses a serious threat to biodiversity and weakens the area's ecological resilience. While Emdrupvej itself is not a key element in reconnecting green corridors, the surrounding neighborhood holds significant potential in this regard, as seen in the report "Grønne Korridorer," created by the local council (Bispebjerg Local Council & DN Copenhagen, 2023). The street could play a supporting role by connecting the green area of Emdrup's Lake to the nearby old baroque park located on the opposite side of Emdrupvej. Enhancing these connections would improve local biodiversity and complement the broader ecological quality of the area.

Figure 2: NO2 ug/m³ levels for Emdrupvej from 2020 (Google map Air view)

Figure 3: Noise mapping from 2017 (City of Copenhagen)

The importance of reconnecting fragmented landscapes in areas like Emdrup is emphasized in the Copenhagen Biodiversity Strategy (Copenhagen Municipality, 2023), which highlights the need for integrated green infrastructure to achieve the city's goal of 30% green and accessible spaces by 2050. The strategy envisions that „in the year 2050, Copenhagen's small and large green areas are bound together by a network of green connections with space for pedestrians, cyclists, and nature,“ reinforcing the city's commitment to enhancing ecological and social connectivity.

2.2.3. Social Diagnosis

Socioeconomic Distribution

The area surrounding Emdrupvej is marked by significant socioeconomic diversity, with the street itself serving as a dividing line between two distinct parts of the neighborhood. On one side, there are single-family villas with private gardens and easy access to the high-quality public space around the Emdrup's lake, a feature that adds to the neighborhood's attractiveness and recreational value. On the other side, there are social housing apartments, reflecting a demographic with generally lower income levels.

Lack of Vibrancy and Community Engagement on Emdrupvej

Surveys conducted by ARUP on Emdrupvej reveal that, although a large majority of respondents frequent the street daily or weekly, most only pass through it and use the street as a transit, highlighting its lack of purpose and attractiveness as a destination (Fig 6 and 7). The lack of attractiveness might be due to different factors. One of them could be that about 73% of the people interviewed sensed a lack of nature on Emdrupvej, highlighting opportunities for improvement of green infrastructures.

Figure 4 : Map of desired green spaces by local council (Bispebjerg Local Council & DN Copenhagen, 2023)

Figure 5: Socio-economic division caused by Emdrupvej

For how long at a time are you typically located on the stretch of road?

Figure 6: Time spent on Emdrupvej by the respondents (ARUP, 2023)

Do you think there is enough nature on the stretch of road Emdrupvej between Tuborgvej and Lyngbyvej?

Figure 8: Respondent's opinion towards the current amount of nature on Emdrupvej.

Figure 9: Respondent's use of the space.

Figure 7: Respondent's use of Emdrupvej (ARUP, 2023)

The survey conducted by the Municipality of Copenhagen also provides meaningful insights into the neighborhood. It reveals that, among all districts in Copenhagen, Rypar-ken-Lundehus has one of the highest rates of perceived insecurity, with 17% of residents reporting feelings of unease in their local area (Figure 9). Additionally, only 15% of respondents agreed that the neighborhood has a thriving business community, reflecting a broader challenge in fostering vibrant and engaging spaces (figure 10). When asked about a strong sense of community, only 28% of respondents agreed, highlighting a significant need to strengthen social cohesion in the area (Figure 11). Tied with social cohesion, 64% of the population believe there are not enough public spaces or are indifferent about the lack of public spaces (Figure 12).

INSECURITY IN NEIGHBOURHOODS

Figure 9: Residents' reported feelings of insecurity, shown by district, highlighting Bispebjerg as having one of the highest rates at 17% (Municipality of Copenhagen, 2021)

THERE IS A THRIVING BUSINESS COMMUNITY

Figure 10: Percentage of residents who agree that the local business community is thriving, revealing low levels of agreement at 15% (Municipality of Copenhagen, 2021)

THERE ARE THRIVING COMMUNITIES

Figure 11: Percentage of residents agreeing with the statement „There are thriving communities,“ revealing low levels of agreement at 28% (Municipality of Copenhagen, 2021).

THERE ARE MANY MEETING AND HANG OUT PLACES

Figure 12: Percentage of residents agreeing with the statement „There are many recreational areas and meeting places“ (Municipality of Copenhagen, 2021)

The diagnosis of Emdrupvej highlights several pressing environmental problems, such as air and noise pollution, urban fragmentation, and significant social challenges including a lack of cohesion, trust, and vibrant public spaces.

Figure 13 summarizes these interconnected issues, illustrating the neighborhood's key challenges and their potential root causes. Citizen participation emerges as a crucial solution to address simultaneously environmental and

social concerns on Emdrupvej. By involving residents, it is possible to co-develop solutions that foster a more resilient and cohesive community while enhancing the area's ecological quality.

Figure 13: Visualization of the diagnostic made for Emdrupvej, showing causes and effects of the two main issues identified.

2.2.4 . Existing strategic framework

This vision for this pilot project at Emdrupvej has been carefully developed to align with the existing plans and strategies adopted by the City of Copenhagen. Addressing the neighborhood's environmental challenges while reducing the city's CO2 emissions and fostering social cohesion directly supports the goals outlined in the municipality's 2025 Climate Plan, as well as its Biodiversity Strategy (Copenhagen Municipality, 2020; 2023). By addressing these key issues, our approach helps build a more sustainable and resilient urban environment at Emdrupvej while aligning with the broader ambitions of the city as a whole. Additionally, through the application of the Doughnut Framework, the strategy aligns with several Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), including SDG 11 (Sustainable Cities and Communities), SDG 13 (Climate Action), and SDG 15 (Life on Land), reinforcing its global relevance and impact (United Nations, n.d.).

Local initiatives

Other stakeholder groups have already recognized the needs and shown interest in Ryparken-Lundehus' potential. Several ongoing initiatives in Emdrup have provided strong data about social and environmental concerns in the area and also citizens' wishes and visions for their neighborhood.

In developing our strategy, we have taken into account the analyses conducted by ARUP and the insights from the Bispebjerg Local Committee. Our objective is to build on and honor existing initiatives while encouraging similar projects in future urban development projects.

ARUP Living lab project (2023)

The Living Lab project by ARUP, focusing on the street Emdrupvej, explores how urban nature can address environmental challenges such as air pollution, noise, and climate resilience while enhancing social cohesion. The initiative involves implementing nature-based solutions like green roofs and vertical rain gardens, aiming to create greener, more livable urban spaces and provide measurable benefits for both the environment and local residents.

Bispebjerg Local Committee „Grønne Korridorer“ (2023)

„Grønne Korridorer“ is a report written collaboratively by the Bispebjerg Local Committee and the Danish Society for Nature Conservation (Danmarks Naturfredningsforening). The goal is to secure strategic green connections throughout the Bispebjerg quarter—where Emdrupvej is located—that enhance biodiversity, recreational opportunities, and cultural heritage for local residents. The report is not placing a lot of focus on Emdrupvej, but recommends connecting the old baroque park with the lake, which is on each side of Emdrupvej (see figure 4).

03 STRATEGIES & METHODS

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3.1 The Doughnut Framework

To address the social and ecological challenges at Emdrupvej and in order to make sustainability experiments as proposed by Copenhagen Municipality, the Doughnut Economy Framework is being introduced. The framework encourages multi-level stakeholders to develop holistic solutions to local problems without compromising global sustainability. In essence, it helps to set a vision for a world where people and the planet can thrive in harmony (DEAL, 2024a; Raworth, 2017).

The center of the Doughnut represents the social foundation—the minimum standards needed for decent human lives. These standards, derived from the United Nations’ Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), ensure dignity, safety, and justice for all.

The outer edge, or ecological ceiling, represents the nine scientifically defined planetary boundaries created by the Stockholm Resilience Center. Staying within these boundaries is essential to slow down ecological disasters and prevent species extinction.

The space between the social foundation and the ecological ceiling is the heart and flesh of the doughnut — it is the safe and just operating space for humanity. In this space, human activity meets basic needs without exceeding ecological limits (Akenji et al., 2021).

If we aim to achieve the goals of the Paris Agreement, the Montreal-Kunming Biodiversity Framework, and the UN’s Sustainable Development Goals, we must ensure that everyone’s needs are met within the planet’s ecological means. However, we are far from achieving this; Globally, billions of people still lack access to basic necessities, while human activity has already breached 6 of the 9 planetary boundaries (Wong et al., 2024). The challenge lies in moving simultaneously toward the Doughnut’s inner boundary—addressing social needs—and its outer bounda-

Figure 15: Planetary boundaries overshoot and social foundation shortfall (Birgisdóttir et al., 2023)

ry-respecting ecological limits. Achieving this balance requires transformative change and innovative action at all levels (Raworth, 2017).

While this is undoubtedly a complex task, cities, and local areas have shown great potential as initiators and testing grounds for transformative change, particularly when citizens are actively engaged (DEAL, 2024b). For this reason, SELC, together with the Copenhagen Municipality, is excited to invite Emdrupvej to become a pilot project for Doughnut experiments.

Figure 14: The Doughnut of social and planetary boundaries (Birgisdóttir et al., 2023)

3.1.1. Copenhagen Municipality's Doughnut

Since 2023, the Copenhagen Municipality has produced an annual status report using the Doughnut Framework. It serves as an informational tool to guide project prioritization during budget discussions and identify areas requiring action where solutions are needed. The CPH Doughnut shows “needs for solutions” in multiple indicators. Copenhagen is overshooting multiple planetary boundaries especially due to high CO2 emissions, land use, biodiversity loss, and nitrogen pollution. It also highlights that Copenhagen has unsolved issues in the social foundation such as mental health, equality, and housing (Copenhagen Municipality, 2024).

As previously mentioned, Emdrupvej will serve as a testing ground for experimenting with solutions to the interconnected challenges outlined in Copenhagen's Doughnut model as well as the context specific challenges outlined earlier in this report. Currently, the available data does not allow for creating a comparable Doughnut model specifically for Emdrupvej. Instead, we will collaborate with local citizens, businesses, the municipality, and other stakeholders, employing multidisciplinary and participatory methods to map and outline the area's unique issues.

Figure 16: Planetary boundary overshoot and social foundation short-fall for Copenhagen Municipality (Copenhagen Municipality, 2024)

"THE GOAL IS TO ADDRESS LOCAL ISSUES
- SUCH AS SOCIAL COHESION AND
ENVIRONMENTAL POLLUTION - WHILE
ALSO CONTRIBUTING TO GLOBAL
SUSTAINABILITY."

3.2. The Method: A Neighborhood Portrait With Four Lenses

The central question we seek to address, in collaboration with multiple stakeholders at Emdrupvej, is:

How can Emdrupvej become a thriving and inclusive home for all, fostering shared spaces for participation, connection, and access to nature, while respecting the wellbeing of all people and the health of the planet?"

We can break this question into four distinct lenses, as recommended by the DEAL methodology, examining each in depth along with their interconnections: the local-social, the local-ecological, the global-social, and the global-ecological (DEAL, 2020).

By taking snapshots of the current situation under the four lenses, we can create what is called a city portrait - or in this case a neighborhood portrait. The portrait can be created in many different ways with the use of soft and hard data, different kinds of knowledge and include a wide range of actors. While a city portrait is never perfect or complete, it is an excellent tool to start discussions about the aspirations for an area and mapping strengths,

Figure 17: The four lenses in the context of Emdrupvej

"The city portrait has proved to be a challenging and thought-provoking starting point to explore the socio-economic and ecological dynamics that are driving consumption-intensive behaviour, lifestyle patterns, and systemic inequalities." (DEAL, 2020)

weaknesses and opportunities for the wellbeing of a city, a neighborhood or a specific project (DEAL, 2020).

The neighborhood portrait can be co-created by multiple changemakers, from municipal authorities and businesses to local residents. This can lead to eye-opening conversations

and realizations as the portraits unlock our common understanding of the space, the challenges and opportunities, and paint a big and multifaceted picture of shared dreams and goals. The lenses' global aspects also have the potential to open up critical conversations about the indirect drivers of ecological destruction and human suffering.

3.2.1 External Examples

Many cities worldwide are experimenting with operationalizing the doughnut framework by using the four lenses for multiple purposes. At Emdrupvej we will build on experiences from other cities and adjust it to the local context and needs of local stakeholders.

Figure 18: Amsterdam Municipality has created a detailed city portrait, pairing present city targets with the most relevant available data. This was done for all four lenses in collaboration with diverse stakeholders. This provided a holistic snapshot of the city and its impact. (City of Amsterdam, 2020)

WHAT WOULD IT MEAN FOR AMSTERDAM TO THRIVE WITHIN ITS NATURAL HABITAT?

Rød: utfordringer
Mørk grønn: løsninger
Lys grønn: potensiale

Figure 19: In Grønlikaia, Norway, a new port-development company has used the four lenses on specific projects, outlining the opportunities, challenges and solutions. This has been done in cooperation with multiple local stakeholders (Hav Eiendom, 2022).

The Principles

When applying the Doughnut Framework, it is essential that any initiative seeking to implement it adheres to the following principles (DEAL, 2024a):

EMBRACE THE 21ST CENTURY GOAL

Aim to meet the needs of all people within the means of the living planet. Seek to align your organisation's purpose, networks, governance, ownership and finance with this goal. Expect the work to be challenging, innovative and transformative.

SEE THE BIG PICTURE

Recognise the potential roles of the household, the commons, the market and the state - and their many synergies - in transforming economies. Ensure that finance serves the work rather than drives it.

NURTURE HUMAN NATURE

Promote diversity, participation, collaboration and reciprocity. Strengthen community networks and work with a spirit of high trust. Care for the wellbeing of the team.

THINK IN SYSTEMS

Experiment, learn, adapt, evolve, and aim for continuous improvement. Be alert to dynamic effects, feedback loops and tipping points.

BE DISTRIBUTIVE

Work in the spirit of open design and share the value created with all who co-create it. Be aware of power and seek to redistribute it to improve equity amongst stakeholders.

BE REGENERATIVE

Aim to work with and within the cycles of the living world. Be a sharer, repairer, regenerator, steward. Reduce travel, minimize flights, be climate and energy smart.

AIM TO THRIVE RATHER THAN TO GROW

Don't let growth become a goal in itself. Know when to let the work spread out via others rather than scale up in size.

Figure 20: Map of key stakeholders

3.3 How We Community Organize

What we organize around is vital, but equally important is how we organize. Without including the right stakeholders in the process, we cannot expect them to embrace, support, or utilize the solutions developed (Agger & Tortzen, 2023). On the other hand, when the right people come together under conducive conditions, we can uncover valuable solutions to the complex and intertwined challenges of the 21st century (Kiss et al, 2021; Raworth, 2017).

Ultimately, the most profound insights and sustainable solutions to these complex challenges can only come from the local citizens and interest groups in the Ryparken-Lundehus neighborhood. All the stakeholders are mapped

out in figure 20. Thus, the most important aspect of this plan is to allocate significant resources to fostering meaningful, effective, and enduring citizen engagement. But our role extends beyond organizing — in SELC we will leverage our expertise and networks to dismantle legal, economic, and other structural barriers that may hinder progress. By addressing these obstacles, we aim to create an inclusive environment where all stakeholders can actively participate in shaping a sustainable and thriving Emdrupvej.

We also suggest that Copenhagen Municipality take an active role in the co-creation of Emdrupvej. Research shows compelling reasons for the municipality to evolve its governance role into that of a more collaborative

partner, supporting co-creation and innovation, and fostering safe, trust-based spaces where citizens, businesses, and other stakeholders can meet and collaborate - also known as mosaic governance (Agger & Tortzen, 2023; Buijs et al., 2019, Gentin et al., 2024).

To address the social and environmental challenges at Emdrupvej, we propose a series of participatory processes designed to foster collaboration, build community, and drive sustainable change. To initiate the conversation, the following chapters will also present examples and ideas for concrete landscape transformations that could serve as practical solutions for the community, thus this would have to be decided in collaboration with the local community.

04 INITIATIVES

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4.1 Activating Democracy

Inspired by participatory initiatives in other Doughnut cities worldwide, we propose a series of initiatives designed to foster inclusive, democratic participation in the revitalization of Emdrupvej. Each initiative serves multiple purposes such as enhancing social cohesion while promoting green upskilling, education, visioning, or deliberation. All initiatives will be guided by the principles of the Doughnut Framework, ensuring that they contribute to both social and ecological sustainability.

The initiatives will be launched and co-facilitated by SELC but with the active involvement of diverse stakeholders from Emdrupvej and the municipality. These actors will be invited to participate in the design process to ensure the initiatives are tailored to the specific needs of local residents and the unique context of the area.

CITIZEN SCIENCE PROJECTS

Local residents can play a crucial role in gathering valuable data about their area to help identify and address local issues. We will initiate projects that involve residents in monitoring biodiversity, collecting data on environmental factors such as air and noise pollution, and contributing to the evaluation of environmental initiatives around Emdrupvej.

DOUGHNUT MINI-PUBLICS

At the heart of our approach is the establishment of Doughnut Mini-publics. A mini-public is a small representative group of citizens convened to deliberate and provide input on public policy or community issues. SELC will host mini-publics with different themes that will bring together a diverse group of local residents, businesses, governmental authorities, experts ect. to deliberate and co-create solutions for Emdrupvej's challenges by using the Doughnut Framework. Initially, the mini-publics will be open for participation; once a mini-public is established, designated contributors will be expected to participate throughout the process. By providing a structured, inclusive platform for dialogue, mini-publics will empower residents, ensure diverse perspectives are heard, delegate responsibility, and build trust and ownership of local projects.

EMDRUPVEJ FESTIVAL FOR COMMUNITY AND SUSTAINABILITY

A vibrant festival aims to kickstart the process by celebrating Emdrupvej's unique identity and aspirations. Featuring doughnut workshops, talks, and interactive activities, the festival will showcase sustainable practices, inspire community participation, and foster a shared vision for the neighborhood.

ECO-INNOVATION HUB

An Eco-Innovation Hub will serve as a space for local entrepreneurs, innovators, and changemakers to collaborate on projects addressing sustainability and social cohesion. By offering resources, networking opportunities, and support, the hub will help incubate ideas that can transform Emdrupvej into a model of sustainable urban living.

SKILL-SHARING SESSIONS

Skill-sharing workshops will enable residents to exchange practical knowledge in areas like gardening, urban green maintenance, repair work, and creative arts. These sessions will build community capacity, promote environmentally friendly living, and strengthen local networks.

URBAN NATURE WALKS AND WORKSHOPS

Educational walks and hands-on workshops will help residents discover the environmental assets of and around Emdrupvej, while teaching ways to protect, enhance and maintain urban biodiversity.

GREEN YOUTH ENGAGEMENT

The area around Emdrupvej is rich with young people. Tailored programs for young residents, including green leadership workshops, eco-education, and creative activities, will create a safe space for participation and empower the next generation to take an active role in shaping Emdrupvej's future.

SUPPER CLUBS

Regular communal meals will be organized to bring residents together in a relaxed and inclusive setting. These supper clubs will provide a space to share stories, discuss local issues, and strengthen social connections.

4.2. Landscape Transformation as Inspiration

At SELC we have allowed ourselves to ask some big and bold What If - questions, to help ignite imagination and creativity before the coming collective reimagination of Emdrupvej, (Hopkins, 2021).

Alongside these visionary questions, we've also explored practical „What now...?“ scenarios, envisioning real-life solutions and transformative ideas that could address these questions. The ideas are crafted to address the challenges of Emdrupvej while staying inside the Doughnut. In this section we present examples of how we have applied the four lenses to test our ideas and offer small sketches that envision the transformation at Emdrupvej.

These ideas are intended to inspire residents and stakeholders to consider potential changes in the physical landscape, not as final solutions but as starting points for further dialogue and development. We hope to empower the local community to develop their own Doughnut-friendly ideas, rooted in their understanding of their community's unique needs and priorities.

„What if Emdrupvej prioritized people over cars?“

„What if Emdrupvej had a welcoming community space for all?“

„What if Emdrupvej flourished with edible plants?“

What if Emdrupvej had a welcoming community space for all?

Imagine Emdrupvej with a dedicated physical space where participatory initiatives can flourish and be anchored—a place where democracy, experimentation, and meaningful conversations thrive. We envision transforming part of the historic piano factory at Emdrupvej 28, a spacious and centrally located site between the lake and the square, into a vibrant community hub. Currently dominated by a large parking lot, the outdoor area in front could likewise be repurposed to serve the common good, benefiting both people and biodiversity.

By acquiring the ground floor of the old piano factory, we could transform the indoor facilities into a dynamic space for volunteer meetings, workshops, and communal activities. It would be a welcoming place for families to attend the supper club, and a venue where people of all ages can gather for mini-publics to deliberate and envision the future of Emdrupvej. The hub could host swap-spots and tool libraries, allowing local residents to exchange clothes, books, or furniture, or borrow tools like drills.

An inviting green outdoor area could be created by de-paving most of the existing parking lot, transforming it into a communal green space. This could be a gathering place for all residents— to smell the herbs and flowers from the flowerbed, to enjoy a drink under the shadow of a tree after a communal event, to play hopscotch and street games with family and friends.

In keeping with the principles of the Doughnut, the space would be developed with minimal resource use, utilizing only reclaimed materials and repurposing the de-paved asphalt for other needs.

Local

Global

Social

Pro: Local community place for democratic participation

Con: Dispute about buying local offices and removing parking

Solution: Radical inclusion before implementation

Pro: Place for promoting socially just initiatives and behavior

Con: -

Solution: Activating the space for events centering global justice

Ecological

Pro: More green, less grey & car infrastructures - biodiversity

Con: Does not make connection to green corridors

Solution: Developing green infrastructure to the entire neighborhood

Pro: Mitigating car emissions

Con: Refurbishing can be resource intensive

Solution: Only use recycled materials

What if Emdrupvej prioritized people over cars?

Imagine looking down Emdrupvej and seeing people sitting, walking, and biking amidst a lush canopy of trees, bushes, and flowers. The melody of birdsongs resonates louder than the hum of car engines.

Bioswales, vegetated ditches with a porous bottom, could serve as a key feature to slow down traffic, reduce noise and air pollution, and manage stormwater runoff. These bioswales would not only enhance stormwater management but also naturally calm traffic by narrowing the roadway. They would provide additional space for planting street trees and vegetation, enriching the streetscape, creating an ecological corridor, and supporting biodiversity by offering habitats for birds and insects. Prioritizing bike lanes and pedestrian pathways would further encourage sustainable transportation, fostering active lifestyles and reducing car dependency.

Establishing bioswales between the old baroque park and the lake would especially offer a unique opportunity to create a seamless connection between the natural areas. This initiative aligns with the principles of the Doughnut Economy by promoting a harmonious balance between ecological health and community well-being.

Local

Social

Pro: healthy environment for humans

Con: Resentment from car users, traffic congestion

Solution: Open discussion

Ecological

Pro: Less noise and air pollution, more water infiltration

Con: -

Solution: informing about the initiative

Global

Pro: Inspiration for car-dieting

Con: Cars will pollute bypass road

Solution: Monitoring

Pro: Mitigating car emissions, biodiversity, more canopy cover

Con: Construction emissions

Solution: Prioritize recycled materials

What if Emdrupvej flourished with edible plants?

Imagine walking along Emdrupvej, greeted by a beautiful diversity of herbs, vegetables, and fruits. Picture yourself stopping by a raised bed to grab a handful of majestic rhubarb stalks on your way home, or digging your fingers into the soil to help clear the bed from weeds together with one of your neighbors.

We envision transforming parking spaces and street corners into communal vegetable gardens and small greenhouses. These shared gardening spaces would address both social and environmental challenges by fostering biodiversity and urban greening while providing communal areas for residents to grow food, exchange knowledge, and build stronger relationships.

This initiative exemplifies tactical urbanism, focusing on small-scale, low-cost gardening interventions that can enhance public spaces along Emdrupvej. It offers a hands-on opportunity to test solutions before considering broader implementation in Ryparken-Lundehus, encouraging community engagement and environmental stewardship.

Local

Global

Social

Pro: Good for mental health and sense of community

Con: Risk that the task is too big for the community

Solution: Investing in capacity building and upskilling

Pro: Inspiration for other neighborhoods

Con: -

Solution: Sharing good and bad experiences with DEAL community

Ecological

Pro: More green, less grey & car infrastructure - biodiversity

Con: Risk of mis-management and introduction of invasive species

Solution: Investing in capacity building and upskilling

Pro: Mitigating car emissions

Con: Construction of beds and greenhouses takes resources and CO2

Solution: Only use used materials

05 IMPLEMENTATION FRAMEWORK

05. IMPLEMENTATION FRAMEWORK

The strategy for Emdrupvej represents a model of urban development that inspires community engagement, co-creation and promotes environmental and social sustainability. At its core, the strategy seeks to rebuild social and organizational networks by strengthening local democracy and decision-making processes. This is achieved through collaborative opportunities, co-visioning, skill-sharing, capacity building, and the joint implementation of sustainable solutions.

The implementation of a Doughnut Strategy for the community surrounding Emdrupvej must adopt a cyclical framework. While traditional urban planning often follows a linear timeline, this project emphasizes a circular process where experimentation, adaptation, and iteration are integral. The implementation framework consists of several phases, beginning with introductory events to familiarize community members with the strategy and progressing through participatory development stages, where ideas are brought to life. Each initiative will be unique in their scale, scope, and resource utilization so there is no prescribed time frame for implantation.

5.1 The Cycle of Co-Creation

Phase 0 – Introduction

The process begins with an opening festival to introduce the pilot project, its principles, and the design concepts for reimagining Emdrupvej. Alongside this, other introductory initiatives will be conducted, such as information campaigns and advertisements, to spark interest, build trust, and mobilize participants for the upcoming participatory activities.

Phase 1 – Sharing, Educating, and Assessing

All initiatives, whether addressing social or environmental issues, start with creating spaces for deliberation. This involves organizing events and activities outlined in section 4.1 that encourage education, creativity, and imagination. Within this phase, comprehensive assessments and community input are central in order to create a neighborhood portrait for Emdrupvej. Through these efforts, the community builds consensus on projects and plans are designed to address specific neighborhood challenges and aspirations.

Phase 2 – Implementation

After reaching consensus, the next phase focuses on implementation and testing. This stage incorporates tactical urbanism and urban interventions, emphasizing non-permanent, low-cost experiments and creative solutions. By utilizing existing resources and semi-per-

manent installations, the community can explore possibilities while minimizing material waste and bureaucratic delays. During this phase, residents live with and test these initiatives, offering feedback on their viability and suggesting necessary adjustments to suit the local context.

Phase 2.5 – Iteration

Based on the outcomes of the testing phase, the process loops back for refinement and improvement. This iterative stage ensures that ideas are optimized and any unintended consequences of the initiatives are addressed. The cycle of adaptation strengthens the overall strategy and its alignment with community needs.

Phase 3 – Monitoring and Management

Once a solution is deemed successful and well-received, it exits the cyclical process and becomes a permanent feature of the community. The final phase emphasizes ongoing monitoring and management to ensure the solution's long-term success and sustainability, maintaining its relevance and value for future generations.

Incorporating citizen science and community stewardship into the project offers an excellent opportunity for community involvement and data collection. By measuring air quality along Emdrupvej, residents can actively par-

ticipate in gathering valuable environmental data, fostering a deeper connection with the project and its goals. Additionally, participatory evaluation methods can be employed to ensure that community members have a say in assessing the outcomes of the initiatives, further enhancing transparency and inclusivity.

5.2. Strategy Evaluation and Dissemination

Measuring, evaluating and learning from this pilot project is key in order to harvest the fruits from the multiple doughnut experiments carried out, and spreading successful doughnut initiatives to the broader Copenhagen. SELC will be responsible for continuing to measure and evaluate the progress of this strategy. Distinct measures for assessing the success of the transformation of Emdrupvej will be used, such as:

- Community engagement and co-creation

Tracking the frequency of community events, the number and diversity of participants and evaluating the quality of the individual events/meetings.

Conduct annual surveys of the community, similar to that of ARUP's research

- Air and noise quality improvements

Measuring the changes in air and noise pollution levels along Emdrupvej

- Increased green space accessibility

Track the expansion of public green areas. Assess resident usage and satisfaction with new green spaces through surveys and usage data.

- Sustainable urban initiatives

Tracking the numbers of citizen led initiatives that are aligned with the doughnut principles. Use surveys to evaluate the individual initiatives among local stakeholders.

After year four of the pilot project, a final report will be released documenting the successes and/or failures of the strategy. The hope is for this project to become embedded in the community and to continue for years to come. After year four, SELC and the Copenhagen Municipality will convene to discuss other viable areas to expand the program.

As the dedicated consultancy for this strategy, SELC will continue to engage with and support the residents of Ryparken-Lundehus and Emdrupvej in the following years to come.

"Adapting our existing local infrastructures - our homes, streets and civic spaces - to host communal dining, caring, growing, and working is a fundamental shift required for reducing further resource extraction and waste." (Civic Square)

06 CONCLUSION

06. CONCLUSION

This strategy is intentionally not a comprehensive plan for a full physical transformation of the Ryparken-Lundehus neighborhood. Instead, it is a proposal to implement a participatory process that fosters social cohesion and ecological renewal for the Ryparken-Lundehus communities. The Doughnut Framework will serve as both the theoretical foundation and a toolbox of methods to diagnose, envision, learn, play, experiment, and implement collaboratively. This approach will guide stakeholders in addressing local social and ecological concerns while remaining mindful of planetary boundaries and the wellbeing of all living beings.

Emdrupvej will serve as a central hub for participation and a laboratory to inspire other Copenhagen communities to organize and engage in strategic planning for nature and wellbeing in their neighborhoods. The methods and governance model outlined in this strategy are also intended to inspire the Municipality of Copenhagen in future city development and planning projects. By enhancing democratic participation and adopting mosaic governance methods, we aim to create a model that not only improves residents' daily lives and strengthens urban green spaces but also builds trust between citizens and local government, leads to more holistic and legitimate solutions, and ultimately gives more power to the people.

This strategy offers concrete examples of how to address specific challenges in Ryparken-Lundehus. However, the ultimate goal is to inspire and empower residents to leverage their local knowledge, forge meaningful connections with neighbors, and drive sustainable and effective changes in their community. At SELC, we are committed to supporting them every step of the way.

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